

Explore what *Investigating in Science* could look like to learn more about the Physical World. (Table adapted from Fenton, 2011)

	Modelling	Classifying and Identifying	Pattern seeking	Making things or developing systems	Observing	Fair testing (scientific method)
This could be...	<input type="checkbox"/> Build a model atom and investigate the significance of electrons being on the outside...what is the connection to how electricity flows along a wire or how static electricity is created? <input type="checkbox"/> Create a story (words, role play, video animation, cartoons) that link familiar everyday concepts to explain physics, eg, how does electricity flow in a circuit? <input type="checkbox"/> Make a model house using different materials to explore physical and chemical properties such as strength, waterproofing, or resistance to colour fading in direct sunlight. <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> What materials create static electricity ? <input type="checkbox"/> How is radiation from mobile phones and cell towers different from other types of radiation? <input type="checkbox"/> finding which metal from a given sample would be most suitable for making a saucepan; <input type="checkbox"/> Which materials are attracted to a magnet? <input type="checkbox"/> What are some everyday examples of transverse waves and longitudinal waves? <input type="checkbox"/> What materials are good conductors? <input type="checkbox"/> What materials are good insulators <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> investigating the behaviour of falling objects and ways of slowing their fall, e.g., paper parachutes <input type="checkbox"/> Make a bottle orchestra to find the pattern that links water level and pitch; <input type="checkbox"/> Record the results of investigations into objects which float or sink; <input type="checkbox"/> Record the results of investigations into making waves in water; <input type="checkbox"/> Investigate the way waves can be generated and how they travel down a slinky spring <input type="checkbox"/> What colours are best at keep an object cool in sunlight?	<input type="checkbox"/> Make simple toys to learn about battery powered circuits <input type="checkbox"/> Learn how to make plaster casts of animal tracks or make "fossils" for your students to identify <input type="checkbox"/> Make a simple data logger for \$10. Use it to detect different types of radiation such as IR or UV. Do sunglasses really block UV? <input type="checkbox"/> Make a simple electric motor or a simple generator <input type="checkbox"/> Research how a primary student turned her science fair project into an classroom invention <input type="checkbox"/> Research how other famous scientists made discoveries 'by luck' (serendipity) <input type="checkbox"/> Create a simple science game or simulator (Mac and PC). <input type="checkbox"/> Build simple play dough powered toys . How can you make them work most efficiently?	<input type="checkbox"/> Make this magnetic bottle and observe the way the iron filings line up. <input type="checkbox"/> Make a human shape from cardboard and using a plumb-line to find the position of its centre of gravity <input type="checkbox"/> Take a torch to pieces to find out how the bulb is connected to the battery; <input type="checkbox"/> Make a shadow puppet with a torch and investigating how to make the shadow bigger; <input type="checkbox"/> How do different animals produce sound? <input type="checkbox"/> How do different animals move in air or the water?	<input type="checkbox"/> Fair testing method <input type="checkbox"/> Deciding if a project is technology or science <input type="checkbox"/> Investigate floating and sinking <input type="checkbox"/> Investigate the effect of sunlight on samples of rubber, ink, and paper. <input type="checkbox"/> Investigate the best conditions for producing a long life battery using salty play dough. <input type="checkbox"/> Investigate the factors which affect the strength of a simple electromagnet; <input type="checkbox"/> Design a "fair test" on the sound insulating properties of different materials used in houses;

Notes:

- The above are a few suggestions only. Please add to this document and save it for your own use on your home computer if you find it useful.
- Observations could be recorded digitally if appropriate; sounds, time lapse still images or motion video clips.
- Observational drawings are to be scientific observational drawings, with no shading. Dots and lines are allowed. The drawing must be done in pencil on A4 paper, with the specimen's name(s) printed in the lower left corner. It should be drawn directly from the observed object(s). A scale must be shown. (from [Taranaki Science Fair website](#))
- Investigations using animals must follow the guidelines outlined in this site [Caring for Animals](#) and the Animal Welfare Act 1999
- Investigations that involve practical work must follow health and safety guidelines as set out in this document ['Safety and Science Guidance Manual'](#)